

1 The cauliflower mosaic virus transmission helper protein P2
2 modifies directly the probing behavior of the aphid vector *Myzus*
3 *persicae* to facilitate transmission

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20

21 **Abstract**

22 There is growing evidence that plant viruses manipulate their hosts and vectors in ways that increase
23 transmission. However, to date only few viral components underlying these phenomena have been
24 identified. Here we show that cauliflower mosaic virus (CaMV) protein P2 modifies the feeding behavior of
25 its aphid vector. P2 is necessary for CaMV transmission because it mediates binding of virus particles to
26 the aphid mouthparts. We compared aphid feeding behavior on plants infected with the wild-type CaMV
27 strain B-JI or with a deletion mutant strain, B-JI Δ P2, which does not produce P2. Only aphids probing B-JI
28 infected plants doubled the number of test punctures during the first contact with the plant, indicating a role
29 of P2. Membrane feeding assays with purified P2 and virus particles confirmed that these viral products
30 alone are sufficient to cause the changes in aphid probing. The behavior modifications were not observed
31 on plants infected with a CaMV mutant expressing P2Rev5, unable to bind to the mouthparts. These results
32 are in favor of a virus manipulation, where attachment of P2 to a specific region in the aphid stylets – the
33 acrostyle – exercises a direct effect on vector behavior at a crucial moment, the first vector contact with the
34 infected plant, which is essential for virus acquisition.

35 **Author summary**

36 Some pathogens including plant viruses manipulate vectors to optimize transmission. The manipulations
37 can be indirect meaning that pathogens alter host traits such as color or odor that attract or deter vectors.
38 Other modifications are direct, i.e. uptake of virus compounds changes vector behaviors. Direct effects
39 have been reported for viruses that are internalized by their vectors and interact strongly with the vector
40 from within, for example with the nervous system. Here we show that contact of a virus protein with the
41 vector's exterior mouthparts suffices to induce a direct effect: binding of the non-structural cauliflower
42 mosaic virus protein P2 to aphid stylets during test punctures modifies probing activity instantly, thereby
43 facilitating virus transmission. The fact that here no intimate virus-vector interactions are required for vector
44 manipulation and transmission, could explain the broad vector range of CaMV and other non-circulative
45 viruses.

46

47 Introduction

48 Plant viruses are economically important pathogens and most of them require a vector for
49 transmission (Bragard et al., 2013). Insects are the most common vectors and, among these,
50 Hemiptera such as aphids, whiteflies, plant- and leafhoppers account for the transmission of the
51 majority of the vector-borne viruses (Ng and Perry, 2004; Ray and Casteel, 2022). This is likely
52 due to their particular mouthparts, the stylets. The stylets' morphology is adapted to piercing-
53 sucking feeding behavior and allows aphids and other hemipterans to acquire and inoculate
54 viruses into plant tissues with great precision and without inflicting major damage.

55 A growing corpus of theoretical modelling and empirical research shows that viruses and other
56 parasites modify hosts and vectors to optimize their transmission (Gandon, 2018; Lefèvre et al.,
57 2006; Mauck et al., 2018; Roosien et al., 2013). These modifications may be referred to as
58 parasitic manipulation when two conditions are met. First, the phenotypic changes in the host or
59 vector enhance the fitness of the pathogen and second, they are under the genetic control of the
60 pathogen (Poulin, 2010). Evidence for the first criterion has been cumulated by numerous studies
61 for plant viruses (Eigenbrode et al., 2018; Mauck et al., 2012). In contrast, the viral factors
62 responsible for changes in vector fitness are often unknown (Mauck et al., 2019). Plant viruses
63 alter host plant phenotype that in turn influences vector attraction and feeding behavior, and
64 consequently virus acquisition (Mauck et al., 2014; Mauck et al., 2016; Mauck et al., 2010). Some
65 viral genes have been implicated in these indirect plant-mediated alterations of vector traits
66 (Arinaitwe et al., 2022; Carr et al., 2020; Westwood et al., 2013; Wu et al., 2017).

67 Viruses can – after acquisition by vectors – also alter vector behavior directly. This has been
68 studied in particular for plant viruses relying on the circulative transmission mode. Such viruses
69 traverse the intestine, cycle through the hemocoel and accumulate in the salivary glands, before
70 inoculation as a saliva component into new plant hosts. During their passage, they can interact
71 with various host organs, for example the brain, the salivary glands or antenna and modify vector
72 behavior in ways that are conducive to virus transmission (Hu et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2020; Wu
73 et al., 2022). Similar manipulations have also been described for other pathogens that replicate
74 in their vectors (Herbison et al., 2018). To the best of our knowledge, there is no evidence that
75 non-circulative viruses, i.e. viruses that bind to vector mouthparts for their passage to a new host,
76 can change vector behavior directly, whereas plant-mediated effects are well-documented (Dáder
77 et al., 2017). One report detected altered feeding behavior on healthy test plants of whiteflies

78 viruliferous with a non-circulative crinivirus, but since the insects were raised for two generations
79 on infected plants before the experiments, plant-mediated effects cannot be excluded (Lu et al.,
80 2019).

81 Cauliflower mosaic virus (genus *Caulimovirus*) is transmitted by aphids using the non-circulative
82 mode. CaMV virions are retained in the aphid mouthparts (stylets) by attaching to cuticular
83 proteins (stylins) located at the stylet tip in a zone called the acrostyle (Uzest et al., 2007; Uzest
84 et al., 2010; Webster et al., 2018). Transient adherence of virions occurs via a helper component,
85 the viral protein P2 (Armour et al., 1983; Lung and Pirone, 1974). P2 forms a protein bridge
86 between the stylets and the virions, most likely by binding with its N-terminus to stylins and with
87 its C-terminus to the virion, more precisely to the capsid-associated viral protein P3 (P3:virions)
88 (Leh, 1999; Leh et al., 2001; Pirone and Blanc, 1996). Aphids can acquire the helper component
89 P2 and P3:virions simultaneously or sequentially, i.e. either preformed P2:P3:virions complexes
90 or first P2 and in a second step P3:virions (Drucker et al., 2002).

91 Aphids landing on a new plant will explore the plant's suitability with test punctures. For this, they
92 insert the stylets in epidermis and mesophyll cells, salivate briefly into the cytoplasm and ingest
93 actively some of the cellular contents. If the plant is susceptible, the stylets advance deeper into
94 the tissue, doing more test punctures until they are inserted into the sieve tubes. Here the feeding
95 behavior changes: after an active salivation phase, the aphids ingest phloem sap passively and
96 continuously, their principal food source. Because P2 locates exclusively in infected cells, it can
97 be acquired only during intracellular test punctures, whereas P3:virions can be acquired during
98 test punctures and during phloem sap ingestion (Palacios et al., 2002).

99 Our previous work showed that CaMV infection of the model plant *Arabidopsis thaliana* caused
100 *Myzus persicae* aphids to feed longer from the phloem, which might enhance the acquisition of
101 P3:virion complexes from the phloem sap. We demonstrated that the P6-TAV protein of CaMV
102 contributes majorly to this altered feeding behavior (Chesnais et al., 2021). P6-TAV is a
103 multifunctional protein responsible for most CaMV symptoms and modifications of the physiology
104 of the host (Pooggin and Ryabova, 2018; Schoelz and Leisner, 2017). Therefore, it is most likely
105 that it exercises an indirect host-mediated effect on the behavior of the aphid vector. We were
106 interested to investigate whether a non-circulative virus like CaMV could also encode factors
107 having a direct effect on the vector. We chose P2 to test for this hypothesis, because it contains
108 the interaction domain for binding to the aphid stylets, making it an excellent candidate.

109 **Results**

110 **Aphid feeding behavior is different on plants infected with wild type CaMV**
 111 **expressing P2**

112 **1. Feeding behavior of *Myzus persicae* on mock-inoculated, JI- or JIΔP2-infected turnip plants.** (a)
 113 Symptoms on turnip leaves at 14 dpi. From left to right, mock-inoculated, JI-infected, JIΔP2-infected leaf.
 114 (b) Western blot analysis of the accumulation of P2 (18 kDa), P4 (37, 44 kDa) and P6-TAV (62 kDa) in JI-
 115 or JIΔP2-infected turnip plants at 14 dpi. Each lane corresponds to a total protein extract from a different
 116 plant. The large RuBisCO subunit is stained by Ponceau S and serves as a loading control. Mock is extract
 117 from a mock-inoculated healthy leaf. (c-d) The behavior of individual aphids was recorded by electrical
 118 penetration graph (EPG) for 8 h on turnip leaves infected or not with the indicated virus (N = 21-24).
 119 Selected EPG parameters are presented sorted according to (c) duration or (d) occurrence. The histogram
 120 bars display means and standard errors. Different letters indicate significant differences between plant
 121 infection status as tested by GLM (generalized linear model) followed by pairwise comparisons using
 122 “emmeans” (p < 0.05 method: Tukey). Statistical analysis of the duration of events indicated significant
 123 differences for the duration of phloem sap ingestion on infected vs healthy plants (GLM, Df = 2, $\chi^2 = 7.776$,
 124 p = 0.020) but no differences for the total duration of stylet penetration (GLM, Df = 2, $\chi^2 = 3.868$, p = 0.145),
 125 the total duration of pathway phase (GLM, Df = 2, $\chi^2 = 4.037$, p = 0.133) and the time to first sap ingestion
 126

127 from phloem (Cox, Df = 2, $\chi^2 = 0.373$ p = 0.185). Statistical analysis of the occurrence of events revealed
128 significant differences for the numbers of stylet penetrations, pathway phases and intracellular test
129 punctures on infected (JI and JI Δ P2) vs mock-inoculated plants (GLM, Df = 2, $\chi^2 = 10.756$; $\chi^2 = 24.948$; χ^2
130 = 37.13, p < 0.001, respectively), and a significant difference for the number of intracellular test punctures
131 during the first stylet penetration on JI-infected plants vs JI Δ P2-infected and mock-inoculated plants (0-
132 inflated model, Df = 2, $\chi^2 = 35.958$, p < 0.001).

133 To test for a possible effect of P2 on aphids, we chose to compare the behavior of aphids on
134 turnip plants infected with wild type CaMV isolate JI or with the CaMV P2 deletion mutant JI Δ P2.
135 We first verified that the deletion did not affect the infectivity of the virus. No difference in
136 symptoms was observed between plants infected with JI or JI Δ P2. All plants displayed
137 characteristic leaf bleaching that initially affected only the veins (mosaics) and that covered later
138 in infection the entire leaf (Figure 1a). Fully infected plants showed, in addition, leaf curling and
139 retarded plant growth. The first symptoms appeared 6 days after mechanical inoculation of plants
140 with the virus and a day later all plants were symptomatic (Supplementary Figure 1). Then, we
141 studied the accumulation of the CaMV proteins P2, capsid protein P4 and P6-TAV by western
142 blot in infected turnips (Figure 1b). As expected, P2 was detected in plants infected with JI, but
143 not in plants infected with JI Δ P2. Accumulation of P4 and P6-TAV was similar in JI and JI Δ P2-
144 infected turnips. Taken together, the deletion of the P2 coding sequence had no impact on the
145 timing and severity of symptoms, and it did not affect CaMV replication as judged by the
146 accumulation of P4 and P6-TAV. Thus, the experimental setup was suited to compare aphid
147 behavior on infected plants expressing P2 vs. those that did not.

148 We placed aphids on mock-inoculated, JI and JI Δ P2-infected plants and used EPG to evaluate
149 the effect of the infection, and more specifically that of the presence of P2, on acquisition feeding
150 behavior (Figure 1c-d). Aphids spent significantly more time ingesting phloem sap on plants
151 infected with JI than on healthy plants (Figure 1c), consistent with our earlier report (Chesnais et
152 al., 2021). Deleting P2 from the viral genome had no effect on phloem sap ingestion. When
153 analyzing the occurrence of events, the total numbers of stylet penetrations, pathway phases and
154 intracellular test punctures were significantly lower on infected plants than on mock-inoculated
155 ones, with no difference between JI and JI Δ P2. However, we observed P2-specific alterations for
156 the number of intracellular punctures during the first probe, which was twice as high on JI-infected
157 plants than on JI Δ P2-infected ones or mock-inoculated ones. Another feeding parameter, the
158 number of phloem sap ingestion phases, was significantly lower on JI-infected plants than on

159 mock-inoculated turnips, their number on JIΔP2-infected leaves was intermediate (GLM, Df = 2,
 160 $\chi^2 = 6.968$, $p = 0.031$). This indicated a possible, but only partial contribution of P2 to this behavior
 161 modification. Taken together, infection with JI and JIΔP2 significantly increased the duration of
 162 phloem sap ingestion. Only wild type infection (i.e. presence of P2) doubled the number of
 163 intracellular punctures in mesophyll and epidermis during the first stylet insertion, indicating that
 164 P2 was associated with this.

165 **Post-acquisition effect of P2-expressing wild type CaMV on aphid inoculation**
 166 **behavior**

167
 168 **Figure 2:** Feeding behavior during inoculation access period (IAP) of *Myzus persicae* on healthy plants
 169 after 1 h acquisition feeding on mock-inoculated, JI-infected or JIΔP2-infected plants (N = 22–26). (a)
 170 presents the duration and (b) the occurrence of behavior phases. The histogram bars show means and
 171 standard errors. Differing letters indicate significant differences between plant infection status as tested by
 172 GLM (generalized linear model) followed by pairwise comparisons using “emmeans” ($p < 0.05$ method:
 173 Tukey). No significant differences were found for the duration of behavior phases (GLM and Cox models,
 174 $p > 0.05$). For the occurrence of events, significant differences were detected for the number of intracellular
 175 test punctures of aphids originating from infected (JI and JIΔP2) vs mock-inoculated plants (GLM, Df = 2,

176 $\chi^2 = 12.629$, $p < 0.001$), for the number of intracellular punctures during first penetration (0-inflated, Df = 2,
177 $\chi^2 = 39.740$, $p < 0.001$) and for the number of stylet penetrations before the first phloem sap ingestion for
178 aphids transferred from JI-infected plants vs those transferred from mock-inoculated plants (GLM, Df = 2,
179 $\chi^2 = 11.353$, $p < 0.001$). (c) Correlation between the number of intracellular test punctures during IAP on
180 healthy plants and the total duration of pathway phase during acquisition access period (AAP) on mock-
181 inoculated (green), JI-infected (dark blue) or JI Δ P2-infected (light blue) plants. The coefficients of
182 correlation are $r = 0.62$, $r = 0.61$ and $r = 0.69$ for mock-inoculated, JI-infected and JI Δ P2-infected plants,
183 respectively.

184 The previous experiment indicated modified aphid feeding behavior on infected plants, i.e. during
185 virus acquisition feeding. We wanted to know whether virus infection and P2 also modifies feeding
186 behavior post-acquisition, i.e. during the inoculation access period. Aphids were allowed a 1 h
187 acquisition access period (AAP) (under EPG control) on mock-inoculated or infected plants and
188 then transferred to healthy test plants for virus inoculation. The feeding behavior was recorded
189 for another 4 h to assess the impact of viruliferous status on aphid behavior. The total duration of
190 all feeding phases was similar for all conditions (Figure 2a). However, we detected differences in
191 the occurrence of three probing parameters (Figure 2b). The total number of test punctures was
192 significantly higher for aphids transferred from infected plants to healthy plants, compared to those
193 originating from mock-inoculated ones. The number of intracellular punctures during the first stylet
194 penetration was significantly lower for aphids transferred from infected plants compared to those
195 transferred from healthy plants. This was due to infection and not to P2 because there was no
196 difference between JI and JI Δ P2 infections. The number of stylet penetrations before the first
197 phloem sap ingestion was elevated for *Myzus persicae* having acquired from JI-infected plants
198 compared to those coming from healthy plants. Aphids having fed previously on JI Δ P2-infected
199 plants required an intermediate number of penetrations until first phloem ingestion. Thus, there
200 may be a tendency for P2 to increase probing events.

201 To better define a potential role of P2 on the aphid probing behavior, we performed a correlation
202 analysis of the behavior of aphids during the 1 h AAP and the 4 h inoculation access periods (IAP)
203 (Figure 2c). The number of intracellular punctures during IAP on healthy plants correlated strongly
204 with the total duration of the pathway phase during AAP on infected plants (Pearson's correlation;
205 $t = 7.988$, Df = 90, $p < 0.001$). Interestingly, the number of intracellular punctures per minute of
206 the pathway phase was similar for aphids coming from healthy plants and JI Δ P2-infected plants,

207 while this number was higher for aphids originating from JI-infected plants (LM, $\chi^2 = 755.500$, Df
 208 = 2, $p = 0.048$). This again is in favor of a role of P2 in modifying aphid probing behavior.

209

210 **Feeding on purified P2 and virus particles modifies aphid probing behavior**

211

212 **Figure 3:** Feeding behavior of *Myzus persicae* on healthy plants after acquisition of P2 and P3:virions in
 213 artificial medium. The histogram bars display means and standard errors. Before recording aphid feeding
 214 behavior on healthy plants, aphids were allowed to feed under electrical penetration graph (EPG) control
 215 for 1 h on different artificial media: 15 % sucrose in water (light grey); 15 % sucrose in DB5 buffer (orange)
 216 or 15 % sucrose (final) in DB5 buffer supplemented with P3 and purified virus particles (P3:virions, dark
 217 grey); his-tagged P2 (HP2, yellow); or HP2 and P3:virions (blue). Purity of the viral components used for
 218 aphid feeding assays on artificial medium is shown in Supplementary Figure 2. Only aphids having inserted
 219 their stylets for at least 5 min in the artificial media were used for the experiments (N = 21-26). Letters
 220 indicate significant differences between artificial media as tested by GLM (generalized linear model)
 221 followed by pairwise comparisons using “emmeans” ($p < 0.05$ method: Tukey). Analysis of behavior
 222 occurrences indicated a significant effect of HP2+P3:virions on the total number of stylet penetrations
 223 (GLM, Df = 4, $\chi^2 = 23.228$, $p < 0.001$), the number of stylet penetrations before the first phloem phase (GLM,

224 Df = 4, $\chi^2 = 20.090$, $p < 0.001$), the number of intracellular test punctures (GLM, Df = 4, $\chi^2 = 72.429$; $p <$
225 0.001) and the number of pathway phases (GLM, Df = 4, $\chi^2 = 21.336$, $p < 0.001$). HP2 alone had a significant
226 effect on the number of intracellular test punctures during the first stylet penetration (0-inflated model, Df =
227 4, $\chi^2 = 72.430$, $p < 0.001$).

228 Our results indicated that P2 altered aphid probing behavior on infected plants. This effect could
229 be direct (P2 protein itself changes aphid behavior), indirect via P2-mediated changes in the host
230 plant, or a combination of both. To test for a direct effect of P2, we allowed aphids to acquire
231 recombinant P2 and purified P3:virions (the components of the CaMV transmissible complex) by
232 membrane feeding on artificial medium. Then they were placed on healthy test plants and their
233 feeding behavior was recorded by EPG (Figure 3). This approach eliminated all plant and virus
234 factors that might modify aphid behavior by indirect action of P2. No significant differences for
235 duration of feeding events were observed (GLM, $p > 0.05$) (Supplementary Figure 3). When
236 analyzing the occurrence of events, we found that the number of phloem sap ingestions was not
237 changed by acquisition of P2 (Table S3). In contrast, the occurrence of several other behavior
238 forms was different. Membrane acquisition of HP2 plus P3:virions increased significantly the total
239 number of stylet penetrations, the number of brief stylet penetrations (< 3 min) (GLM, Df = 4, $\chi^2 =$
240 19.636 , $p < 0.001$, Supplementary Table 3), and the number of stylet penetrations before the first
241 phloem sap ingestion. Further, HP2 plus P3:virions augmented the number of intracellular test
242 punctures and the number of intercellular pathway phases significantly. In general, the effect of
243 HP2 plus P3:virions on aphid behavior was stronger than that of HP2 alone. An exception was
244 the number of test punctures during the first stylet penetration that was significantly enhanced
245 only for HP2.

246 Aphids feeding on plants infected with a CaMV mutant that expresses a P2 deficient in
 247 stylet binding show mostly normal probing behavior

248
 249 **Figure 4:** Probing behavior of aphids on turnips infected with non-transmissible JI-P2Rev5. (a) Mock-
 250 inoculated, JI- and JI-P2Rev5-infected turnip leaves at 14 dpi. (b) Western blot analysis of the accumulation
 251 of P2 (18 kDa), P4 (37, 44 kDa) and P6-TAV (62 kDa) in JI- or JI-P2Rev5-infected turnip plants at 14 dpi.
 252 Total leaf extracts from 5 infected plants per condition were analyzed. Ponceau S staining of the large
 253 RuBisCO subunit is shown as a loading control. Mock, extract from mock-inoculated leaf. (c) Feeding
 254 behavior of *Myzus persicae* on mock-inoculated, JI- or JI-P2Rev5-infected turnip plants at 14 dpi. The
 255 histogram bars present means and standard errors. The behavior of individual aphids was recorded by
 256 electrical penetration graph (EPG) for 4 h (N = 26-28). Different letters indicate significant differences
 257 between plant infection status as tested by GLM (generalized linear model), followed by pairwise
 258 comparisons using “emmeans” (p < 0.05 method: Tukey). The number of intracellular punctures during the
 259 first penetration is significantly higher for JI-infected vs mock- and JI-P2Rev5-infected plants (0-inflated
 260 model, Df = 2, $\chi^2 = 77.32$, p < 0.001). The number of penetrations before first sap ingestion is significantly
 261 lower for JI-infected compared to mock-inoculated plants (GLM, Df = 2, $\chi^2 = 13.709$, p = 0.001). The total
 262 number of intracellular punctures is similar for aphids on JI-infected and mock-inoculated turnips, but
 263 elevated for JI-P2Rev5-infected plants (GLM, Df = 2, $\chi^2 = 23.692$, p < 0.001). Statistical analysis revealed

264 no differences for the number of stylet penetrations and pathway phases (GLM, Df = 2, $\chi^2 = 1.146$, $\chi^2 =$
265 5.452, p = 0.059 and 0.065, respectively).

266 Our results from the feeding experiment with artificial medium suggest a direct effect of P2 on
267 aphid behavior. At this point, we consider two non-mutually exclusive hypotheses. P2 could
268 modify behavior by binding to the stylets or by interacting with vector factors in the more posterior
269 parts of the digestive tract. To test the first hypothesis, we used the mutant protein P2Rev5, which
270 contains a single Q→Y mutation at amino acid position 6, which abolishes P2 interaction with the
271 stylets, but maintains all other properties of P2 (Moreno et al., 2005). Since the original P2Rev5
272 mutation was characterized in the CaMV CabbS background, we introduced the mutation into the
273 JI genome and obtained the CaMV mutant JI-P2Rev5. Turnip plants infected with JI-P2Rev5
274 displayed symptoms identical to the wild type-infected plants (Figure 4a). Accumulation of the
275 capsid protein P4 and P6-TAV was identical in JI and JI-P2Rev5-infected plants (Figure 4b).
276 However, P2 accumulation was somewhat lower in JI-P2Rev5-infected plants than in wild type-
277 infected plants (Figure 4b).

278 Infection with JI-P2Rev5 being similar to wild type virus infection, we assessed aphid behavior on
279 JI-P2Rev5-infected turnip plants. Like in the previous experiment (Figure 1), no virus effect on the
280 duration of probing events was found (see Supplementary Figure 4), so only those related to
281 occurrence are shown here. Aphids on JI-infected plants performed more than twice as many
282 intracellular punctures during the first stylet penetration than on JI-P2Rev5-infected or healthy
283 plants (GLM, 0-inflated model, Df = 2, $\chi^2 = 77.32$, p < 0.001), which is the same result as obtained
284 with JI Δ P2 (Figure 1).

285 The number of aphid stylet penetrations and pathway phases was lower on JI-infected plants than
286 on JI-P2Rev5-infected or healthy plants. This was similar as in Figure 1, but whereas there the
287 differences were statistically significant they were here marginally insignificant (GLM, Df = 2, χ^2
288 = 1.146, $\chi^2 = 5.452$, p = 0.059 and 0.065, respectively). The number of penetrations before the
289 first phloem feeding was significantly reduced for JI, but not for JI-P2Rev5, compared to mock-
290 inoculated plants (GLM, Df = 2, $\chi^2 = 13.709$, p = 0.001). Except for the total number of intracellular
291 punctures which was slightly (~10 %) but significantly elevated for JI-P2Rev5, compared to JI and
292 healthy plants, aphid probing behavior was very similar on JI-P2Rev5-infected and mock-
293 inoculated plants. To sum up, the aphid behavior modifications observed for JI were not found for
294 P2Rev5, in particular the twofold increase in the number of intracellular punctures during the first

295 penetration. The observed behavioral changes indicate that the acrostyle-binding capacity of P2
296 is important for this. This is supported by the fact that a CaMV isolate harboring the P2Rev5
297 mutation is not transmissible (Moreno et al., 2005) and that recombinant GFP-tagged P2Rev5
298 does not bind to dissected stylets in in vitro interaction assays (Uzest et al., 2007). We set up
299 membrane feeding assays using baculovirus-expressed P2Rev5 to confirm these observations.
300 Unfortunately, the results were not conclusive, probably because we could use for this experiment
301 only crude P2 extracts containing many contaminating proteins and other compounds
302 (Supplementary Figure 5; Supplementary Table 5).

303 Discussion

304 CaMV infection alters the overall aphid feeding behavior, while the P2 helper component
305 modulates aphid probing behavior

306 Analysis of feeding behavior on infected plants showed significant modification of three feeding
307 activities that are directly related with CaMV acquisition (Figure 1). One, the duration of phloem
308 ingestion increased, two, the total number of test punctures during the entire eight hour
309 observation period decreased, while, three, their number during the first stylet penetration
310 doubled.

311 Prolonged phloem ingestion might be advantageous for CaMV transmission because the phloem
312 sap contains virus particles and uptake of CaMV from the phloem has been reported before
313 (Palacios et al., 2002). Prolonged phloem ingestion was observed previously with the same CaMV
314 isolate on two other hosts, *Arabidopsis thaliana* and *Camelina sativa* (Chesnais et al., 2021). This
315 could therefore highlight potential adaptive virus effects. The second observation, reduction of
316 intracellular test punctures over the entire observation period, might be considered
317 counterproductive to acquisition because it should decrease chances to acquire P2, which is
318 absent from the sieve tubes. However, the work by Palacios and coworkers showed that
319 combined uptake of CaMV from tissue and phloem sap might even be more efficient than uptake
320 from epidermis and mesophyll cells alone. Thus, potential negative effects of decreased
321 intracellular test punctures seem to be outweighed by earlier and longer phloem ingestion. This
322 differentiates CaMV from typical non-circulative viruses that are acquired during test punctures in
323 the tissue and lost rapidly when vectors reach the phloem (see for example (Wang and Ghabrial,
324 2002). These two parameters, phloem ingestion and total number of test punctures, were altered
325 similarly for aphids feeding on plants infected with JI and with JIΔP2. This demonstrates that P2

326 plays no role in this and that other viral factors are involved. A candidate is P6-TAV, which
327 contributes to the modification of aphid feeding behavior although it alone is not sufficient to
328 induce all behavior changes (Chesnais et al., 2021).

329 The third parameter, the number of test punctures during the first stylet penetration, was doubled
330 on plants infected by JI, but not on healthy plants or those infected by JI Δ P2. As removing the
331 coding sequence of P2 from the CaMV genome did not affect other parameters of the infection
332 (Figure 1), we suggest that the increase in test punctures during the first penetration may be
333 caused exclusively by P2. Test punctures are mandatory for acquisition of P2 (which is found only
334 in epidermis and mesophyll cells (Palacios et al., 2002)) and their increase during the first stylet
335 penetration might speed up P2 acquisition and consequently the acquisition of P3:virions. Virus
336 acquisition during the first stylet penetration is also favorable for virus transmission by non-host
337 aphids that reject incompatible plants after the first test punctures and leave them (Fereres et al.,
338 1993; Pitt et al., 2022). Carmo-Sousa et al. (Carmo-Sousa et al., 2014) reported similar results
339 for the non-circulative cucumber mosaic virus (CMV). They observed that aphids exhibited during
340 the first 15 minutes – but not later – twice as many test punctures on CMV-infected plants than
341 on mock-inoculated plants. Therefore, this change in aphid behavior during its first contact with
342 the infected plant may be very important for the acquisition of viruses transmitted in a non-
343 circulative manner like CaMV and CMV. An interesting point is that the behavior change is in both
344 cases immediate since it is observed from the very first test punctures onwards. This suggests
345 that the ‘active compound’ does not need to traverse the digestive tract to induce behavior
346 modification.

347 We also studied aphid inoculation behavior. We found no differences in phloem feeding behavior
348 of *M. persicae* on healthy test plants, no matter whether the aphids had fed before on mock-
349 inoculated, JI-infected or JI Δ P2-infected plants. This is expected because the phloem feeding
350 behavior is essentially influenced by plant quality and phloem sap composition (Dinant et al.,
351 2010), and this is similar for all healthy inoculation plants. However, some relevant probing
352 parameters were modified. First, the total number of test punctures was higher for aphids coming
353 from infected plants compared to those from mock-inoculated ones. There was no difference
354 between JI and JI Δ P2, indicating that not P2 but other viral or plant factors increased the number
355 of test punctures. Second, the number of stylet penetrations before the first phloem sap ingestion
356 was higher when aphids had previously fed on JI-infected plants compared to mock-inoculated

357 plants, whereas this number was intermediate after acquisition feeding JIΔP2-infected plants. P2
358 might therefore be partially involved in the modification of this parameter. Furthermore, the
359 correlation between the number of intracellular punctures on healthy inoculation plants and the
360 duration of the pathway phase on infected JI but not JIΔP2 acquisition plants (Figure 2c) suggests
361 that P2 (i.e. JI-infected turnips) alters subsequent aphid probing behavior. The increased number
362 of probes and intracellular punctures on a healthy plant by CaMV-carrying aphids might increase
363 the chances for successful inoculation and be beneficial for transmission.

364 Evidence for a direct effect of P2 on aphid behavior

365 P2 might directly or indirectly change aphid probing behavior. Our membrane feeding assays
366 present evidence for a direct effect of P2. Aphids having acquired different combinations of
367 purified P2 or P3:virions through feeding on the artificial medium (thus excluding any interference
368 from other plant or virus factors), showed altered subsequent probing behavior, compared to
369 aphids that had access artificial medium without viral compounds (Figure 3). Compared to
370 inoculation feeding on healthy test plants after CaMV acquisition from infected plants (Figure 2),
371 inoculation feeding after membrane feeding changed more behavioral parameters. We propose
372 that this is due to the unphysiological conditions of the artificial feeding medium (high salt content,
373 presence of detergent), necessary to maintain P2 active (Hébrard et al., 2001). Therefore,
374 although the membrane feeding experiments do show a direct effect of P2 on aphids,
375 interpretation of the altered behaviors is difficult.

376 Hypotheses on the mode of action of P2

377 How could P2 change aphid probing behavior? P2 binds to a specific region in the stylets, the
378 acrostyle in the common canal in the stylet tips (Forbes, 1969; Uzest et al., 2007; Uzest et al.,
379 2010). The acrostyle at the tip of the maxillary stylets is very restricted in size (~0.2 μm x 5 μm)
380 and located in a stylet region whose diameter does not exceed ~0.5 μm (Uzest et al., 2010).
381 Binding of P2 and especially of P3:virions (about 35-60 nm in diameter) (Nikolai et al., 2015;
382 Plisson et al., 2005) might cause steric hindrance and impede the flows in the common channel
383 during the active ingestion phases (i.e. intracellular test punctures (Tjallingii and Hogen-Esch,
384 1993)). The changed probing behavior might be an effort of the aphid to compensate for this. In
385 favor of this hypothesis is that membrane acquisition of P2 plus P3:virions had globally a stronger
386 effect on aphid probing behavior than P2 alone. Furthermore, P2 is known to form long
387 paracrystalline filaments that even alone could induce some alteration of the flux in the common

388 canal (Blanc et al., 1993; Hébrard et al., 2001). We observed no effect of P2 on phloem ingestion.
389 An explanation is that this feeding behavior is passive and driven by the high hydrostatic pressure
390 of the phloem sap, which might outweigh steric hindrance effects (Froelich et al., 2011). An
391 alternative, but not mutually exclusive hypothesis is that binding of P2 or transmissible complexes
392 to the acrostyle affects stylet proteins. The acrostyle is covered with cuticular proteins entangled
393 with the chitin fibers of the stylets (Ioannidou et al., 2014). Two of these proteins (called stylins)
394 have been identified and at least one of them – Stylin-1 – can interact with P2 (Webster et al.,
395 2018). The binding of P2 to stylins might interfere with their natural function, which is yet unknown.
396 The lack of nerve cells in the maxillary stylets harboring the acrostyle makes it implausible that
397 stylins are signaling receptors and that P2 binding is perceived as a signal (Forbes, 1966).
398 Instead, P2 might displace or compete with attachment of natural stylin ligands – for example
399 saliva effectors (Deshoux et al., 2022) – thus making foraging for the aphid more difficult and
400 resulting in an increased number of test punctures (Wang et al., 2021; Will et al., 2013). It is
401 interesting to note that the binding of P2 to the acrostyle and the concomitant changes in aphid
402 behavior is evidence that the acrostyle is needed for proper probing activity. P2 might also
403 exercise an effect by binding further down in the digestive tract. However, we believe this is
404 unlikely because aphids on plants infected with the JI-P2Rev5 mutant, which abolishes interaction
405 with the acrostyle, displayed similar behavior as those on mock-inoculated or JIΔP2-infected
406 plants. In particular, they did not show the twofold increase in intracellular punctures during the
407 first stylet penetration (compare Figures 1b and 4c). Taken together, aphid behavior on JIΔP2-
408 and JI-P2Rev5-infected plants seems to show that the interaction of P2 with the acrostyle stylin
409 increases frequency of some characteristic aphid probing behaviors facilitating an efficient virus
410 acquisition.

411 [Concluding remarks](#)

412 To our knowledge, a direct and immediate effect on vector behavior of a protein from a virus or
413 other pathogen by simple binding to the latter's mouthparts has not been reported before. The
414 protozoan parasite *Leishmania* infects the gut of its sand fly vector and secretes a gelling protein
415 that together with promastigotes obstructs and damages the mouthparts and gut, inciting the sand
416 fly to increase biting frequency on mammal hosts and with it transmission (Rogers and Bates,
417 2007). A similar 'plugging' phenomenon is observed for transmission of the bacterium *Yersinia*
418 *pestis* by flea vectors (Hinnebusch et al., 2021). However, there are significant differences to

419 CaMV. First, *Leishmania* and *Yersinia* infect their vectors and establish rather intimate
420 relationships with them, contrary to non-circulative CaMV. Second, the *Leishmania* and *Yersinia*
421 gelling proteins are produced on-site in the intestine, whereas P2 production takes place
422 exclusively in the plant host and seems to affect vector behavior only during and shortly after the
423 vector-host encounter. Thus, the 'site of assault' on the vector is distinctly different in the CaMV
424 pathosystem. It would be interesting to explore whether other plant and animal viruses and other
425 pathogens modify vectors directly through host-expressed pathogen factors, as this could be a
426 means to broaden vector specificity since the intimate interactions to prepare subsequent
427 transmission (in this case allocation of P2) take place in the host and not in the vector (as for
428 circulative viruses). This type of manipulation would appear particularly relevant for non-circulative
429 viruses such as CaMV that are transmitted generally by numerous aphid vector species (at least
430 27 for CaMV, (Bak and Emerson, 2020)). This could impact transmission biology and related
431 fields.

432 Materials and methods

433 Plant growth and virus inoculation

434 Turnip seeds (*Brassica rapa* L. var. "Just Right") were provided by Takii Europe B.V. (de Kwakel,
435 Netherlands), sown in TS 3 fine substrate (Klasmann-Deilmann, Geeste, Germany) in pots (70
436 mm x 70 mm x 65 mm) and cultivated at 8 h light / 16 h dark photoperiod at $20 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. Plants were
437 inoculated at the first true leaf stage (9-day-old) and then grown under 14/10 h light/dark cycle at
438 $20 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. Plants were used for experimentation 14 ± 2 days post-inoculation (dpi), when they
439 showed clear symptoms. Initial mechanical inoculation was performed with infectious plasmids.
440 Subsequent inoculations were mechanical and used plant extracts prepared from infected turnips.
441 For this, 1 g of infected leaves (21 dpi) were ground with 1 ml 10 mM HEPES pH 7.2 and
442 carborundum and rub-inoculated on 9-day-old turnip seedlings.

443 Infectious plasmids

444 Infectious plasmids for initial inoculation of turnip plantlets were pGreen-35S-B-JI (Khelifa et al.,
445 2010) and pGreen-35S-B-JI- Δ P2 (Then et al., 2021) that encode the CaMV Cabb B-JI wild type
446 sequence (called JI in the text) (Delseny and Hull, 1983) and a mutant virus sequence where the
447 P2 sequence is deleted and replaced by an *Apal* restriction site (referred to as JI Δ P2 in the text),

448 respectively, both under control of the 35S promoter. For construction of pGreen-35S-B-JI-
449 P2Rev5, containing a Q→R mutation of amino acid 6 of P2 (Moreno et al., 2005) the P2 sequence
450 of JI was PCR-amplified with Q5 polymerase (NEB, Evry, France) with primers 5'-
451 AGAGGGGCCCATGAGCATTACGGGTT**ACCCGCATG**-3' and 5'-
452 TTAGGGGCCCTTAGCCAATAATATTCTTTAATCC-3' containing the P2Rev5 mutation (in bold)
453 and 5' and 3' *Apal* restriction sites (underlined). The amplicon was gel-purified (Machery-Nagel,
454 Hoerd, France) digested with *Apal* (NEB) and ligated with T2 ligase (Promega, Charbonnières-
455 les-Bains, France) into pGreen-35S-B-JI-ΔP2 cut with the same restriction enzyme and gel-
456 purified. *Escherichia coli* XL10-Gold were transformed with the ligation product, recombinant
457 colonies identified by colony PCR, and the P2 sequence verified by Sanger sequencing.

458 Aphid rearing

459 The *Myzus persicae* (Sulzer) (Hemiptera: *Aphididae*) clone was originally isolated in the
460 Netherlands. Aphids were reared on Chinese cabbage (*Brassica rapa* L. *pekinensis* var.
461 “Granaat”) in a growth chamber at 20 ± 1 °C and a 14/10 h light/dark photoperiod.

462 Aphid feeding behavior

463 The electrical penetration graph DC-system (EPG) was used as described by (Tjallingii, 1988) to
464 investigate the effects of CaMV infection on the feeding behavior of *M. persicae*. To integrate one
465 aphid and one plant into an electrical circuit, a thin gold wire electrode (12.5 μm diameter and 2
466 cm long) was attached with water-based silver glue to the dorsum of an adult apterous aphid that
467 had been immobilized on a 10 μl pipette tip by applying a slight negative air pressure with a
468 vacuum pump. Eight aphids were connected to the Giga-8 DC-EPG amplifier (EPG Systems,
469 Wageningen, Netherlands) and each one was placed directly on the adaxial leaf surface of an
470 individual turnip plant. A second copper rod electrode was inserted into the soil of each potted
471 plant to close the electrical circuit. For the EPG experiments “Acquisition feeding experiment” and
472 “JI-P2Rev5 experiment”, the recordings were performed continuously for 8 h and 4 h respectively,
473 during the photophase inside a Faraday cage at 21 ± 1 °C. In the second EPG experiment
474 (“Inoculation feeding experiment”), aphids’ probing and feeding behaviors were recorded two
475 times. First, aphids were allowed a 1 h acquisition access period on a test plant (either mock-
476 inoculated, JI-infected or JIΔP2-infected). Then the aphid (still attached to the gold wire) was
477 moved to a healthy plant for a 4 h inoculation access period. In the third EPG experiment (“Artificial

478 medium experiment”), aphids were first allowed to feed on an artificial medium during a 1 h
479 acquisition access period and then moved onto a healthy plant for a 4 h inoculation access period.
480 For this setup, the second electrode (copper wire) was inserted in 20 µl medium contained in a
481 sachet formed by two Parafilm membranes spanned over a plastic ring. The feeding medium
482 consisted of 15 % sucrose in water or 15 % sucrose in DB5 buffer, to which virus components
483 were added as indicated. Acquisition and analysis of the EPG waveforms were carried out with
484 PROBE 3.5 software (EPG Systems). Relevant aphid behavior EPG parameters were calculated
485 with EPG-Calc 6.1 software (Giordanengo, 2014) and were based on the different EPG
486 waveforms described by Tjallingii and Hogen Esch (1993). Aphids that produced signals (i.e. total
487 duration of stylet penetration) for less than 5 h out of 8 h in the first EPG experiment (or 2.5 h out
488 of the 4 h recordings in the second, third and fourth EPG experiments) were excluded from the
489 analysis. This criterion was set at 30 min for the AAP duration on plants whereas for aphids on
490 artificial medium, the threshold was 5 min. For an example of an EPG waveform for aphids on a
491 plant or artificial medium, see Supplementary Figures 6 and 7.

492 Statistical analysis

493 The proportion of plants expressing symptoms was analyzed using a Pearson’s chi-squared test
494 with Yates’s correction ($p < 0.05$). Data on the number of days until the appearance of symptoms
495 on infected turnip plants was not normally distributed. Therefore, we used a non-parametric
496 Wilcoxon rank-sum test ($p < 0.05$).

497 We used Generalized Linear Model (GLM) with the likelihood ratio and the chi-squared (χ^2) test
498 to determine a statistically significant difference for EPG data. As feeding duration parameters
499 were not normally distributed we used GLM using a gamma (link = “inverse”) distribution. Because
500 of the large number of 0’s for the “Intracellular punctures during the first penetration” parameter,
501 we used the “zeroinfl” function based on a zero-inflated Poisson model (R package: “pscl”).
502 Parameter “time to first sap ingestion” was modelled using the Cox proportional hazards (CPH)
503 model and we treated cases where the given event did not occur as censored. The assumption
504 of the validity of proportional hazards was checked using the functions “coxph” and “cox.zph”,
505 respectively (R packages: “survival” and “RVAideMemoire”). When a significant effect was
506 detected, a pairwise comparison using estimated marginal means (R package “emmeans”; p-
507 value adjustment with Tukey method) at the 0.05 significance level was used to test for differences

508 between treatments (p-values are shown in Supplementary Table 6). A total of 28 EPG
509 parameters were calculated (Supplementary Tables 1-3).

510 Correlation between EPG parameters from inoculated or healthy plants was carried out with a
511 Linear Model (LM). A pairwise comparison using estimated marginal means (R package
512 “emmeans”; p-value adjustment with Tukey method) at the 0.05 significance level was used to
513 test for differences between the three treatments. The coefficient of correlation (“r”) was calculated
514 by the function cor.test.

515 The application conditions of all LM and GLM were verified by inspecting residuals and QQ plots.
516 All statistical analyses were performed using R software v. 4.0.5 (www.r-project.org/).

517 Western Blot analysis of infected plants and artificial feeding media

518 Total protein extracts were prepared from leaves as described previously (Chesnais et al., 2021),
519 separated by 15 % (P2 and P4) or 12 % (P6-TAV) SDS polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis under
520 reducing conditions and transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes as described in (Towbin et
521 al., 1979). Western blots were performed using antisera raised against P2, P4 and P6-TAV (all
522 diluted 1:2,000, (Chesnais et al., 2021)). Secondary antibodies were horseradish peroxidase
523 conjugates, which were used at a 1:10,000 dilution. The same blot was cut into two stripes to test
524 simultaneously for P2 and P4. Bound antibodies were revealed by enhanced chemiluminescence
525 using a G-Box.

526 Purification of recombinant proteins and virions

527 N-terminal his-tagged P2 (HP2) was expressed in baculovirus-infected *Sf9* cells as described
528 previously (Hébrard et al., 2001). Cells from three 75 cm² cell culture flasks were harvested by
529 centrifugation for 5 min at 500 g and lysed in 9 ml DB5 buffer (50 mM HEPES pH 8.0, 500 mM
530 Li₂SO₄, 0.5 mM EGTA, 0.2 % CHAPS) supplemented with SigmaFast Protease Inhibitor (EDTA-
531 free) and frozen at -80 °C until purification. For purification, the thawed cell lysate was centrifuged
532 for 20 min at 24,000 g and the supernatant charged on a column loaded with 300 µl Ni-NTA resin
533 (Macherey-Nagel) pre-equilibrated with DB5. The column was washed with 5 ml DB5
534 supplemented with 25 mM imidazole. HP2 was eluted with DB5 supplemented with 250 mM
535 imidazole, the protein-containing fractions combined and the imidazole removed by gel filtration

536 with a Sephadex G25 column. Purity and concentration of HP2 were estimated by Instant Blue
537 staining of gels after SDS-PAGE, using BSA as standard.

538 Wild type P3 was purified from *E. coli* BL21 cells as described (Plisson et al., 2005). Briefly, cells
539 induced with 1 mM IPTG for 4 h were harvested by centrifugation for 15 min at 4,000 g, washed
540 once with PBS and the pellets were frozen and stored at -80 °C. Cells were lysed by
541 ultrasonication in PBS pH 8 supplemented with 15 % glycerol, 0.2 mM DTT, 0.1 % Tween20 and
542 SigmaFast Protease Inhibitor (EDTA-free) and centrifuged for 10 min at 18,000 g. The
543 supernatant was heated for 10 min at 65 °C and insoluble proteins were removed by centrifugation
544 for 15 min at 18,000 g. Finally, P3 was purified by differential ammonium sulfate precipitation from
545 25-40 % saturation and ammonium sulphate removed by gel filtration with Sephadex G25 or
546 ultrafiltration with a Vivaspin column.

547 CaMV particles were purified essentially following the protocol of Gömec described previously
548 (Hull et al., 1976). One hundred grams of infected turnip leaves were homogenized in two volumes
549 of phosphate buffer (0.5 M KH₂PO₄ pH 7.2, 7.5 g/l Na₂O₃) and filtered through four layers of
550 cheesecloth and one layer of Miracloth. Urea and Triton X-100 were added to final concentrations
551 of 1 M and 2.5 %, respectively, and the sap was stirred overnight at 4 °C. Then the liquid was
552 clarified by centrifugation for 10 min at 5,000 g and the supernatant was centrifuged for 70 min at
553 110,000 g. The pellets were resuspended overnight at 4 °C in 12 ml 10 mM HEPES pH 7.2. After
554 centrifugation for 5 min at 10,000 g, the supernatants were loaded on 10-40 % sucrose gradients
555 in water and centrifuged for 3 h at 100,000 g in a swing-out rotor. The whitish band visible in the
556 gradients by transillumination was collected with a Pasteur pipette, diluted 1:3 with water and
557 centrifuged for 70 min at 110,000 g. The pellets containing the virus were resuspended in 10 mM
558 HEPES pH 7.2.

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816 Figure legends

817 **Figure 1.** Feeding behavior of *Myzus persicae* on mock-inoculated, JI- or JIΔP2-infected turnip plants. (a)
818 Symptoms on turnip leaves at 14 dpi. From left to right, mock-inoculated, JI-infected, JIΔP2-infected leaf.
819 (b) Western blot analysis of the accumulation of P2 (18 kDa), P4 (37, 44 kDa) and P6-TAV (62 kDa) in JI-
820 or JIΔP2-infected turnip plants at 14 dpi. Each lane corresponds to a total protein extract from a different
821 plant. The large RuBisCO subunit is stained by Ponceau S and serves as a loading control. Mock is extract
822 from a mock-inoculated healthy leaf. (c-d) The behavior of individual aphids was recorded by electrical
823 penetration graph (EPG) for 8 h on turnip leaves infected or not with the indicated virus (N = 21-24).
824 Selected EPG parameters are presented sorted according to (c) duration or (d) occurrence. The histogram
825 bars display means and standard errors. Different letters indicate significant differences between plant
826 infection status as tested by GLM (generalized linear model) followed by pairwise comparisons using
827 “emmeans” ($p < 0.05$ method: Tukey). Statistical analysis of the duration of events indicated significant
828 differences for the duration of phloem sap ingestion on infected vs healthy plants (GLM, Df = 2, $\chi^2 = 7.776$,
829 $p = 0.020$) but no differences for the total duration of stylet penetration (GLM, Df = 2, $\chi^2 = 3.868$, $p = 0.145$),
830 the total duration of pathway phase (GLM, Df = 2, $\chi^2 = 4.037$, $p = 0.133$) and the time to first sap ingestion
831 from phloem (Cox, Df = 2, $\chi^2 = 0.373$ $p = 0.185$). Statistical analysis of the occurrence of events revealed
832 significant differences for the numbers of stylet penetrations, pathway phases and intracellular test
833 punctures on infected (JI and JIΔP2) vs mock-inoculated plants (GLM, Df = 2, $\chi^2 = 10.756$; $\chi^2 = 24.948$; χ^2
834 = 37.13, $p < 0.001$, respectively), and a significant difference for the number of intracellular test punctures
835 during the first stylet penetration on JI-infected plants vs JIΔP2-infected and mock-inoculated plants (0-
836 inflated model, Df = 2, $\chi^2 = 35.958$, $p < 0.001$).

837 **Figure 2:** Feeding behavior during inoculation access period (IAP) of *Myzus persicae* on healthy plants
838 after 1 h acquisition feeding on mock-inoculated, JI-infected or JIΔP2-infected plants (N = 22–26). (a)
839 presents the duration and (b) the occurrence of behavior phases. The histogram bars show means and
840 standard errors. Differing letters indicate significant differences between plant infection status as tested by
841 GLM (generalized linear model) followed by pairwise comparisons using “emmeans” ($p < 0.05$ method:
842 Tukey). No significant differences were found for the duration of behavior phases (GLM and Cox models,
843 $p > 0.05$). For the occurrence of events, significant differences were detected for the number of intracellular
844 test punctures of aphids originating from infected (JI and JIΔP2) vs mock-inoculated plants (GLM, Df = 2,
845 $\chi^2 = 12.629$, $p < 0.001$), for the number of intracellular punctures during first penetration (0-inflated, Df = 2,
846 $\chi^2 = 39.740$, $p < 0.001$) and for the number of stylet penetrations before the first phloem sap ingestion for
847 aphids transferred from JI-infected plants vs those transferred from mock-inoculated plants (GLM, Df = 2,
848 $\chi^2 = 11.353$, $p < 0.001$). (c) Correlation between the number of intracellular test punctures during IAP on
849 healthy plants and the total duration of pathway phase during acquisition access period (AAP) on mock-
850 inoculated (green), JI-infected (dark blue) or JIΔP2-infected (light blue) plants. The coefficients of

851 correlation are $r = 0.62$, $r = 0.61$ and $r = 0.69$ for mock-inoculated, JI-infected and JIΔP2-infected plants,
852 respectively.

853 **Figure 3:** Feeding behavior of *Myzus persicae* on healthy plants after acquisition of P2 and P3:virions in
854 artificial medium. The histogram bars display means and standard errors. Before recording aphid feeding
855 behavior on healthy plants, aphids were allowed to feed under electrical penetration graph (EPG) control
856 for 1 h on different artificial media: 15 % sucrose in water (light grey); 15 % sucrose in DB5 buffer (orange)
857 or 15 % sucrose (final) in DB5 buffer supplemented with P3 and purified virus particles (P3:virions, dark
858 grey); his-tagged P2 (HP2, yellow); or HP2 and P3:virions (blue). Purity of the viral components used for
859 aphid feeding assays on artificial medium is shown in Supplementary Figure 2. Only aphids having inserted
860 their stylets for at least 5 min in the artificial media were used for the experiments (N = 21-26). Letters
861 indicate significant differences between artificial media as tested by GLM (generalized linear model)
862 followed by pairwise comparisons using “emmeans” ($p < 0.05$ method: Tukey). Analysis of behavior
863 occurrences indicated a significant effect of HP2+P3:virions on the total number of stylet penetrations
864 (GLM, Df = 4, $\chi^2 = 23.228$, $p < 0.001$), the number of stylet penetrations before the first phloem phase (GLM,
865 Df = 4, $\chi^2 = 20.090$, $p < 0.001$), the number of intracellular test punctures (GLM, Df = 4, $\chi^2 = 72.429$; $p <$
866 0.001) and the number of pathway phases (GLM, Df = 4, $\chi^2 = 21.336$, $p < 0.001$). HP2 alone had a significant
867 effect on the number of intracellular test punctures during the first stylet penetration (0-inflated model, Df =
868 4, $\chi^2 = 72.430$, $p < 0.001$).

869 **Figure 4:** Probing behavior of aphids on turnips infected with non-transmissible JI-P2Rev5. (a) Mock-
870 inoculated, JI- and JI-P2Rev5-infected turnip leaves at 14 dpi. (b) Western blot analysis of the accumulation
871 of P2 (18 kDa), P4 (37, 44 kDa) and P6-TAV (62 kDa) in JI- or JI-P2Rev5-infected turnip plants at 14 dpi.
872 Total leaf extracts from 5 infected plants per condition were analyzed. Ponceau S staining of the large
873 RuBisCO subunit is shown as a loading control. Mock, extract from mock-inoculated leaf. (c) Feeding
874 behavior of *Myzus persicae* on mock-inoculated, JI- or JI-P2Rev5-infected turnip plants at 14 dpi. The
875 histogram bars present means and standard errors. The behavior of individual aphids was recorded by
876 electrical penetration graph (EPG) for 4 h (N = 26-28). Different letters indicate significant differences
877 between plant infection status as tested by GLM (generalized linear model), followed by pairwise
878 comparisons using “emmeans” ($p < 0.05$ method: Tukey). The number of intracellular punctures during the
879 first penetration is significantly higher for JI-infected vs mock- and JI-P2Rev5-infected plants (0-inflated
880 model, Df = 2, $\chi^2 = 77.32$, $p < 0.001$). The number of penetrations before first sap ingestion is significantly
881 lower for JI-infected compared to mock-inoculated plants (GLM, Df = 2, $\chi^2 = 13.709$, $p = 0.001$). The total
882 number of intracellular punctures is similar for aphids on JI-infected and mock-inoculated turnips, but
883 elevated for JI-P2Rev5-infected plants (GLM, Df = 2, $\chi^2 = 23.692$, $p < 0.001$). Statistical analysis revealed

884 no differences for the number of stylet penetrations and pathway phases (GLM, Df = 2, $\chi^2 = 1.146$, $\chi^2 =$
885 5.452, $p = 0.059$ and 0.065 , respectively).

886 **Figure S1.** Kinetics of symptom onset on turnip plants after mechanical inoculation with leaf extracts
887 revealed no significant differences between JI and JI Δ P2, neither for the percentage of infected plants (N
888 = 29 - 30) (Pearson's Chi-squared test, $\chi^2 = 0.01$, Df = 1, $p = 0.92$) nor the day of symptom onset (Wilcoxon
889 rank sum test, $W = 437$, $p = 0.970$).

890 **Figure S2.** Viral components used for aphid feeding assays on artificial medium. (a) Instant Blue stained
891 protein gel after SDS-PAGE. The slots were loaded with the indicated components. (b) Western blot
892 analysis of purified recombinant his-tagged P2 (HP2), partially purified recombinant P3, and purified virus
893 particles. The blots developed with the indicated antisera.

894 **Figure S3.** Feeding behavior of *Myzus persicae* on healthy plants after membrane acquisition of P2 and
895 P3:virions, bars show means and standard errors. Before recording aphid feeding behavior on healthy
896 plants, aphids were allowed to feed under EPG control for 1 h on different artificial media: 15 % sucrose in
897 DB5 buffer (light grey); DB5 buffer alone (orange) or DB5 buffer supplemented with P3 and purified virus
898 particles (P3:virions, dark grey); his-tagged P2 (HP2, yellow); or HP2 and P3:virions (blue). Viral
899 components used for aphid feeding assays on artificial medium are shown in supplementary Figure 3. Only
900 aphids having inserted their stylets for at least 5 min in the artificial media were used for the experiments
901 (N = 21-26). EPG parameters related to duration are displayed. Letters indicate significant differences
902 between artificial media as tested by GLM (generalized linear model) followed by pairwise comparisons
903 using "emmeans" ($p < 0.05$ method: Tukey).

904 **Figure S4.** Feeding behavior of *Myzus persicae* on mock-inoculated, JI- or JI-P2Rev5-infected turnip plants
905 at 14 dpi, bars show means and standard errors. The behavior of individual aphids was recorded by
906 electrical penetration graph (EPG) for 4 h (N = 26-28). EPG parameters related to duration are displayed.
907 Different letters indicate significant differences between plant infection status as tested by GLM
908 (generalized linear model) followed by pairwise comparisons using "emmeans" ($p < 0.05$ method: Tukey).

909 **Figure S5.** Effect of recombinant P2Rev5 on aphid behavior, bars show means and standard errors. (a-b)
910 Feeding behavior of *Myzus persicae* on healthy plants after membrane acquisition of wild type P2 and
911 P3:virions (P2+P3:virions), P2 carrying the mutation Rev5 and P3:virions (P2Rev5+P3:virions) or of an
912 irrelevant protein (CLINK). Before recording aphid feeding behavior on healthy plants, aphids were allowed
913 to feed under EPG control for 1 h on the different artificial media. Only aphids having inserted their stylets
914 for at least 5 min in the artificial media were used for the experiments (N = 29-34). Selected EPG parameters
915 are presented sorted according to (a) duration or (b) occurrence. Different letters show significant
916 differences between treatments as tested by GLM (generalized linear model) followed by pairwise
917 comparisons using "emmeans" ($p < 0.05$ method: Tukey). (a) Statistical analysis of the duration of events
918 revealed no difference for parameters shown (GLM, $p > 0.05$). (b) Statistical analysis of the occurrence of
919 events revealed significant differences for the numbers of intracellular punctures during first penetration
920 and total intracellular punctures (GLM, Df = 2, $\chi^2 = 95.247$, $\chi^2 = 49.683$, $p < 0.001$, respectively). None of
921 the other statistically processed parameters showed a significant difference between treatment (see
922 Supplementary Table 5). (c) Instant Blue stained protein gel after SDS-PAGE of Sf9 crude extracts used
923 for aphid feeding assays on artificial medium. Black arrows point to the position of P2 and P2Rev5, P2:GFP
924 and P2Rev5:GFP, and CLINK, respectively. P2:GFP and P2Rev5:GFP were not used in our experiment.

925 **Figure S6.** Example of a typical EPG waveform recorded on a leaf. The aphid inserted the stylets into
926 tissue after a few seconds (red arrow) and did probing during the rest of the record (red line). In
927 chronological order, behaviors recorded were a pathway phase (dark grey line) with interspersed

928 intracellular test punctures (green arrows), then salivation into the phloem (medium grey line), and finally
929 a long period of passive phloem sap ingestion (light grey line).

930 **Figure S7.** Typical EPG waveform recorded during membrane feeding. At each insertion of the aphid stylets
931 into the artificial medium a signal was observed (red line). Thus, the duration of presence or absence of
932 aphid stylets in the medium could be measured but no behavior phases could be discerned. This might
933 have been due to the high conductivity of the DB5 buffer that was used as a medium..